

“A DFT Study on the Structural and Intermolecular Interaction of Corylin and Daidzein in Neuraminidase receptor”

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ABSTRACT

The successful practice of medicinal chemistry crucially depending upon the understanding of the principles of protein-ligand interactions. Importantly, the polar, hydrophobic and hydrogen bonding interactions are the most probable type of interactions exist between the protein-ligand complexes. In the present study, a theoretical analysis of Corylin and Daidzein molecule was performed from the wave function obtained from the HF and DFT methods with the basis set 6-311G**. The molecular geometric parameters were predicted by DFT method, which are found to be slightly higher than the HF method and the gas phase is compared with active site. A molecular docking and HOMO-LUMO have been carried out to understand the conformational change in the active site of Neuraminidase Receptor. The nearest neighbours, shortest intermolecular contacts between Corylin and Daidzein - Neuraminidase Receptor and the lowest binding energy of Corylin and Daidzein have been analyzed from the docking analysis.

Further, the electrostatic properties of the molecules also determined. The electrostatic potential (ESP) map of the molecules allows identifying the nucleophilic and electrophilic regions of the molecule. The molecular orbital contributions were studied by using the total (TDOS), partial (PDOS), and overlap population (OPDOS) density of states. The theoretical harmonic vibrational frequencies and scaled values were calculated and compared with experimental Fourier Transform infrared (FT-IR) and Fourier Transform Raman (FT-Raman) spectra.